

Effect of wave action on the rehabilitation success of the brown mussel *Perna perna* in Coffee Bay

By

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ABSTRACT

The study looked at the effect of wave action on the rehabilitation success of the brown mussels *Perna perna* in Coffee Bay. There is a Mussel Rehabilitation Project which attaches mussels onto the rocks and rehabilitation of mussels is considered as good in some sites and bad in some site. One possible reason for that difference between sites could be the effect of wave action. Wave action was measured in six sites along the coast of Coffee Bay between Umtata River mouth and Hole In The Wall. Wave action was measured using cement blocks (water movement), dynamometers (wave force) and local perception of wave action. There was a positive correlation between wave action and rehabilitation success of brown mussels in Coffee Bay. The wave force was higher in good sites than in bad sites. Nqutheni is the best site for rehabilitation and it has highest wave force. There was also more water movement in good sites for rehabilitation. Local people in Coffee Bay use sites that are closer to them, hence they were unable to rank all the sites. People from the north of Coffee Bay were unable to rank sites from the south of Coffee Bay and *vice versa*. Therefore local perception of wave action could not be used to determine the effect of wave action on mussel rehabilitation in this study. It has been found that it is possible to find high water movement in good sites and high water movement in bad sites and *vice versa*. The wave force was higher in good sites than in bad sites. Nqutheni is the best sites for rehabilitation and it has highest wave force. There was relation and correlation between wave action and rehabilitation success of brown mussels in *Coffee Bay*. In conclusion, it can be said that wave action has an effect on mussel rehabilitation of the brown mussels *P. perna* in Coffee Bay.

Key words: *Perna perna*, mussels, wave action, wave force, water movement, indigenous knowledge, rehabilitation

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Figure1. Study sites along the coast of Coffee Bay

Table 1. *t*- test table of the rehabilitation success in Ocean and Lwandlana.

Mean (Lwandlana)	Mean (Ocean)	t-value	df	P
62.56% (\pm SD 5.66)	68.27% (\pm SD 11.13)	-1.58376	22	0.127519

Figure 2. Mean (+SD) weight loss between sites

Table 2. Two way ANOVA table

Source of variation	SS	Degrees of freedom	F	P
Months	0.4380	3	64.41	< 0.05
Site	0.3315	5	29.25	< 0.05
Months*Site	0.0640	15	1.88	< 0.05
Error	0.1496	66		

Figure 3. Mean (+SD) weight loss between months

Figure 4. Wave (+SD) force between sites

Table 3. Results of MRP staff ranking sites according to their perception of wave force.

Site	STAFF									
	Staff 1	Staff 2	Staff 3	Staff 4	Staff 5	Staff 6	Staff 7	Staff 8	Staff 9	Staff 10
Nqutheni	4	1	3	-	2	5	1	4	4	-
Macosana	1	2	1	-	1	3	2	1	5	2
Ocean	3	3	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	3
Lwandlana	2	-	-	1	4	1	4	2	1	1
Mthini	-	-	-	2	-	2	-	-	2	-

Table 4. Sites ranked according to rehabilitation success based on MRP data, wave force and water movement (1 = highest to 5 = lowest).

Rank	Rehabilitation success (MRPdata)	Wave force	Water movement
1	Nqutheni	Nqutheni	Macosana
2	Macosana	Macosana	Lwandlana
3	Ocean	Ocean	Ocean
4	Mthini West	Lwandlana	Mthini West
5	Lwandlana	Mthini West	Nqutheni
6	Mthini East	Mthini East	Mthini East

Table 5. Sites arranged according to the degree of water movement from high to low water movement.

Wave action	Site	Rehabilitation Status
High water movement	Macosana	-Good
High water movement	Lwandlana	-Bad
High water movement	Ocean	-Good
Low water movement	Mthini West	-Bad
Low water movement	Nqutheni	-Good
Low water movement	Mthini East	-Bad

Table 6. Sites arranged according to the degree of wave force from high to low wave force.

Wave action	Site	Rehabilitation Status
High wave force	Nqutheni	-Good
Low wave force	Macosana	-Good
Low wave force	Ocean	-Good
Low wave force	Lwandlana	-Bad
Low wave force	Mthini North	-Bad
Low wave force	Mthini South	-Bad

1. INTRODUCTION

Mussels are ecosystem engineers in marine benthic systems (Borthagaray & Carranza 2007). They live in the intertidal and sub-tidal zone (Bayne 1976; Beadman *et al.* 2004; Erlandsson *et al.* 2005; Porri *et al.* 2006; Helson *et al.* 2007). They are usually found clumping together on wave washed rocks, the clumping habit helps hold the mussels firm against the force of waves (Ruppert *et al.* 2004). Individual mussels attach to the rock by byssal threads (Ruppert *et al.* 2004; Alfaro 2006; Shin *et al.* 2008). The byssal thread is a bundle of strong protein threads made of keratin extending from the base of the foot to the substratum (Ruppert *et al.* 2004). Each byssus thread is about the size of human hair, longer threads have higher tensile strength and thicker threads are more difficult to cut than thinner threads (Shin *et al.* 2008).

The mussel shell consists of two similar convex valves. The shell is longer than its wideness, it supports soft tissues and provides protection from predators (Ruppert & Barnes 1994; Shin *et al.* 2008) and against desiccation. The opening of the valves is controlled by an adductor muscles (Ruppert & Barnes 1994).

Mussels are filter feeders, they feed on free floating seston (Beadman *et al.* 2004; Ruppert *et al.* 2004; Ren & Ross 2005; Helson *et al.* 2007). Low seston production can cause mussel distribution to be limited (Helson *et al.* 2007). Mussels generate currents to draw water in and out through the beating of cilia. Water enters in through an incurrent siphon and wastewater exits through an excurrent siphon (Ren & Ross 2005).

There are many organisms that feed on mussels (Helson *et al.* 2007), such as starfish, whelks (Cheung *et al.* 2004; Dahloff & Menge 1996), crabs (Borthagaray & Carranza 2007; Shin *et al.* 2008) and humans (Hockey & Bosman 1986). Indigenous people of the east coast of South Africa have been feeding on mussels for thousands of years (Hockey & Bosman 1986; Lasiak 1991a; Lasiak 1993; Rius *et al.* 2006).

The coastal strip of the former Transkei homeland in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa is known as the Wild Coast. The Wild Coast is about 300 km long and is widely known for its natural beauty and its ecological importance. It is also known for the extreme poverty experienced by its

rural residents (Kepe & Kobokana 2008). Shellfish harvesting along this coast is done mainly for subsistence purposes, people remove mussels and other intertidal organisms to supplement their diet. Several studies along the Wild Coast in South Africa have shown that the brown mussel *Perna perna* is always the most targeted shellfish organism (Siegfried *et al.* 1985; Lasiak 1991a; Lasiak 1991b; Rius *et al.* 2006). According to Siegfried *et al.* (1985) *Perna perna* constitutes 91.7 % of organisms transported home by local people. There has been an increase in pressure on the coastal resources in the later part of the 20th century, caused by high degree of unemployment and an increase in human population in the region (Dye & Dyantyi 2002). Law enforcement is poor due to the inaccessibility of most coastal areas, thus the majority of the area is not effectively protected and harvesters collect more than legal bag limits. This has led to decline in the abundance of many species, such as brown mussel and limpets.

Natural mussel beds have been replaced in the most accessible areas by patches of coralline algae (Dye & Dyantyi 2002). This presents a problem since once an area has been denuded of mussels, settlement of new recruits is practically impossible (Dye & Dyantyi 2002). To solve this problem, researchers at Unutra (currently Walter Sisulu University) developed a technique to reattach mussels back to the bare rocks in areas where they had been overexploited. Settlement and growth of rehabilitated mussels was similar to those of natural mussel beds (Dye & Dyantyi 2002). This technique is now being used by the Mussel Rehabilitation Project (MRP) in Coffee Bay (Calvo-Ugarteburu, personal communication). The MRP started in Coffee Bay in December 2000 with the aim of rehabilitating over exploited mussel stocks and establishing a local community based/ co-management plan for their sustainable utilization. For the past 8 years MRP staff and members of the Coffee Bay community have been re-attaching mussels onto denuded shores. They have noticed that some sites are good for rehabilitation and some are bad. One possible reason for this difference between sites could be the effect of wave action.

There is numerous literature showing that wave action has an effect in the distribution of marine organisms (Palumbi 1984; Dahlhoff & Menge 1996; Steffani & Branch 2003a; Alfaro 2006). Hydrodynamic forces exist along sites exposed to wave action (Avery & Etter 2006) and have direct and indirect effects on organisms (Denny 1999). It has been observed that in exposed sites a common form of physical disturbance is the dislodgement of mussels by wave action (Steffani & Branch

2003a; Prowse & Pile 2005). Consequently in exposed site mussels have to expend more energy in increasing the thickness of the shell and replacing the byssus thread, which can consume up to 25% to 50% and 8% to 15% of the energy respectively, thus leading to reduced growth (Steffani & Branch 2003b). On the other hand, in exposed sites mussels have better feeding opportunities because water brings food particles to sessile organisms (Dahlhoff & Menge 1996). In sheltered sites the food supply is lower but food resident time is longer than on exposed sites and there is less energy used for maintenance (Steffani & Branch 2003b), thus mussels may be able to use their energy for other biological activities rather than increasing byssus thread attachment (Steffani & Branch 2003a & c). Wave action has also an influence on the larval settlement, it has been found that settlement increases where there is high water flow (Borthagaray & Carranza 2007).

One of the aims of this study was to determine whether there is a relation between wave action and rehabilitation success of the brown mussel *Perna perna* in Coffee Bay. Should there be a relation, wave action could be used to select good sites for rehabilitation. Measuring wave action is expensive and time consuming, hence the second aim of this study was to determine whether local knowledge could determine wave action between sites. Should local knowledge be able to determine wave action between sites, it could be used to select good sites for rehabilitation.

Local knowledge is the knowledge or skill of local people developed through their interaction with the environment. Cinner & Aswani (2007) suggested that scientist should encourage the hybridization of local knowledge and scientific knowledge. Local knowledge can contribute to local empowerment and provide valuable input for alternative natural resource management strategies. Although local knowledge is good it has its limitations, so researchers should not believe whatever indigenous or local people do or say (Elevitch 2004). It is useful to distinguish whether the knowledge is fact-based or value based (Failing *et al.* 2007).

2. HYPOTHESIS

H₀₁: Wave action does not have an effect on rehabilitation success in Coffee Bay.

H_{A1}: Wave action has an effect on rehabilitation success in Coffee Bay.

H₀₂: There is no correlation between local knowledge and scientific knowledge with respect to wave action.

H_{A2}: There is correlation between local knowledge and scientific knowledge with respect to wave action.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. STUDY SITES

The study has been done in Coffee Bay, between Hole in the Wall and the Umtata River mouth. Coffee Bay is situated in the Eastern Cape Province, the poorest province in South Africa and it has poor infrastructure and high level of unemployment (Kepe & Kobokana 2008). Six sites were selected with the help of staff of Mussel Rehabilitation Project (MRP). Three of the sites (Ocean S 31° 58' 45.5" E 029° 09' 20.4", Macosana S 31° 59' 20.8" E 029° 08' 56.6 and Nqutheni S 29° 8' 51" E 32° 0' 12.42") were considered by MRP staff as good sites for rehabilitation and the other three (Mthini East S 31° 57' 20.6" E 029° 11' 01.6", Mthini West S 31° 57' 20.6" E 029° 11' 01.6" and Lwandlana S 31° 58' 39.2" E 29° 09' 43.6") were considered as bad sites (Figure 1).

Figure1. Study sites along the coast of Coffee Bay

3. 2. REHABILITATION SUCCESS

Mussels were rehabilitated at two sites, Ocean and Lwandlana. Ocean is considered as a good site for rehabilitation by MRP staff and Lwandlana is considered as a bad site for rehabilitation. 80 small mussels (between 20-30mm) were placed inside 30cm long half sections of perforated PVC drainage

pipes. 12 pipes were attached in each site by drilling 2 holes per pipe on the rocks using a battery powered Hilti TE 7-A drill with a number 8 drill bit. Nylon plugs (8mm × 40mm) were inserted into the holes and the pipes were attached to the plugs with couch screws. Care was taken to ensure that the mussels were held firmly inside the pipe but they were able to open their valves. The pipes were removed after a month and the rehabilitation success was measured by estimating the percentage of surviving mussels in each pipe every month.

3.3. WAVE ACTION

Wave action was measured once a month between July and October on 6 sites (3 were considered as good and 3 as bad), using three different methods.

3.3.1. Cement blocks

Cement blocks were made by pouring fast anchoring cement, Rockset, into ice cube trays (42mm×44mm×25mm). Each block was glued to a metal plate and holes were drilled through the plates for attachment to the rocks. The plates with attached blocks were dried for 12 hours at 62° C and weighed. Six plates were attached on each site by inserting couch screws through the holes on the plate onto holes drilled on the rocks. The blocks were removed after 24 hours, re-dried for 12 hours at 62°C and weighed. The difference in weight was recorded. It was assumed that the bigger the weight loss the stronger the water movement (Doty 1971).

3.3.2. Dynamometers

Dynamometers were constructed using a modification of Palumbi's (1984). This method has been used also by McQuaid & Lindsay (2000) and Steffani & Branch (2003b). A cable tie (392×4.7 mm) was cut 20mm from the sliding head. A 70mm × 7mm piece of surgical tube (Foley catheter 2-15ml) was tied to the 20mm long tab remaining on the head with a thin wire, the other end of the surgical tube was tied on to a thick wire that had a loop at the end to attach on the rocks. The end piece of the cable tie was thread through the sliding head in its normal orientation (so that the sliding head will move unidirectional, along the cable ribbon) and tied onto the surgical tube and the thick wire. The head was set 265mm away from the free end of the cable tie. A plastic bath plug of 40mm diameter was tied to the 20mm long remaining tab on the head of the cable tie with 100mm fishing line (22kg). Six dynamometers were fixed on the rocks in each site for a period of 24 hours by inserting a couch

screw through the loop on the thick wire and into a hole that had been drilled on the rocks. As the tide came in the waves pushed against the bath plug and the head moved along the cable tie. The length travelled by the sliding head was measured and recorded. It was assumed that the longer the length travelled by the head along the tab, the higher the wave force applied against the bath plug. In order to calibrate the dynamometers, the cable ties of 5 dynamometers were marked at 5mm intervals and the dynamometers were attached to the floor. A spring scale was used to pull the bath plug and move the head of the cable tie from mark to mark. The kilograms used to move the head were recorded at each 5mm mark and the force was expressed in Nm^{-2} .

3. 3. 3. Local perception of wave action

MRP staff were asked to rank all six sites according to their perception of wave action. This was intended to be done among harvesters but harvesters from North of Coffee Bay did not know the sites in the South of Coffee Bay and *vice versa*.

3. 4. STATISTIC ANALYSES

All sets of data were tested for normality using Shapiro – Wilk’s W test. Rehabilitation success was analysed using *t* test after arc-sine transformation. Arc-sine transformation is used to transform data which is in the form of ratio and percentages (Sokal & Rohlf 1995). The data for water movement (weight loss) was analysed using 2 way ANOVA after logarithmic transformation and the data for wave force was analysed using Kruskal Wallis test. Kruskal-Wallis test is used to analyze the data which does not fit assumption of normal distributed data, with more than two independent groups, and groups with and or unequal number of sizes (Sokal & Rohlf 1995). The data has unequal number of sizes because some of the dynamometers were damaged by wave action. Spearman’s rank correlation test (McKillup 2005) was used to determine whether there is a correlation between rehabilitation success and wave action.

4. RESULTS

4.1. REHABILITATION SUCCESS

The average survival rate in Ocean was 68.27% and in Lwandlana was 62.56% immediately after the removal of pipes. Results of the *t* test showed that the percentage of surviving mussels was the same between the two sites $p > 0.05$ (Table 1).

Table 1. *t*- test table of the rehabilitation success in Ocean and Lwandlana.

Mean (Lwandlana)	Mean (Ocean)	t-value	df	P
62.56% (\pm SD 5.66)	68.27% (\pm SD 11.13)	-1.58376	22	0.127519

Survival rate was intended to be estimated once per month for a period of six months from May to October but soon after the removal of pipes all the mussels were washed away and the study could not continue.

4. 2. WAVE ACTION

4. 2. 1. Water movement

The average weight loss varied between 13.00g and 19.48g in different sites (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Mean (+SD) weight loss between sites

Two way ANOVA showed there were differences between sites (Table 2). Post hoc test (Turkey HSD test) showed that Lwandlana (C), Ocean (X) and Macosana (Y) had significantly higher water movement ($p < 0.05$) than the other three sites. There were no significant differences between Mthini West (B) and Nqutheni (Z) ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2. Two way ANOVA table

Source of variation	SS	Degrees of freedom	F	P
Months	0.4380	3	64.41	< 0.05
Site	0.3315	5	29.25	< 0.05
Months*Site	0.0640	15	1.88	< 0.05
Error	0.1496	66		

The average weight loss between months was 15.00g in July, 17.67g in August, 21.58g September and 14.15g in October (Figure 4). Results of two way ANOVA showed that there were differences in water movement between months, post hoc test (Turkey HSD test) showed that water movement was significantly higher in August and September than in July and October ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Mean (+SD) weight loss between months

4. 2. 2. Wave force

The average wave force varied between 17,306.15 Nm^{-2} and 75.894.91 Nm^{-2} in different sites (Figure 4). Kruskal-Wallis test showed there were differences in wave force between sites ($p < 0.05$), with

Nqutheni having significantly higher force. This was due to the one dynamometer in September, which measured a higher wave force than the rest of dynamometers, that was $647,629.23 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$ compared to other dynamometers which measured wave force between $13,000 \text{ Nm}^{-2} - 48,000 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$.if we take this data out of the analysis, Nqutheni still has a significantly higher wave force ($28,250.38 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$).

Figure 4. Wave (+SD) force between sites

Average wave force between months was $20,969 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$ in August, $44,294 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$ in September and $21,238 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$ in October. Kruskal-Wallis showed there were no differences in wave force between months ($p > 0.05$). In July the cable ties were 115mm long and the head travelled the whole length of the cable tie and out, thus wave force could not be measured. However we would say the force was greater than ($86,755 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$). For other months the length of the cable ties were increased to 265mm and the maximum force recorded was $647,629 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$.

4. 2. 3. Local perception of wave action

The local perception of wave action could not be used in the study because MRP staff members as in the case of harvesters were unable to rank all the sites according to wave action. Staff members from the North of Coffee Bay did not know the sites in the South of Coffee Bay and *vice versa* (Table 3).

Table 3. Results of MRP staff ranking sites according to their perception of wave force.

Site	STAFF									
	Staff 1	Staff 2	Staff 3	Staff 4	Staff 5	Staff 6	Staff 7	Staff 8	Staff 9	Staff 10
Nqutheni	4	1	3	-	2	5	1	4	4	-
Macosana	1	2	1	-	1	3	2	1	5	2
Ocean	3	3	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	3
Lwandlana	2	-	-	1	4	1	4	2	1	1
Mthini	-	-	-	2	-	2	-	-	2	-

Mthini East and Mthini West were considered as 1 site because they were close to each other about 100m apart.

4.3. CORRELATION BETWEEN WAVE ACTION AND REHABILITATION SUCCESS

All sites were ranked from 1 to 5 according to their rehabilitation success, wave force and water movement (Table 4).

Table 4. Sites ranked according to rehabilitation success based on MRP data, wave force and water movement (1 = highest to 5 = lowest).

Rank	Rehabilitation success (MRPdata)	Wave force	Water movement
1	Nqutheni	Nqutheni	Macosana
2	Macosana	Macosana	Lwandlana
3	Ocean	Ocean	Ocean
4	Mthini West	Lwandlana	Mthini West
5	Lwandlana	Mthini West	Nqutheni
6	Mthini East	Mthini East	Mthini East

Spearman's rank correlation has shown a strong correlation between wave force and rehabilitation success ($\rho_s=0.94$). There was a weak correlation between water movement and rehabilitation success ($\rho_s =0.24$).

5. DISCUSSION

The attachment of mussels was the same in Lwandlana and Ocean immediately after the removal of PVC drainage pipes ($p > 0.05$). Those results were expected since mussels were placed under the pipes and held firmly, as result waves could not wash them away. The method (Dye & Dyantyi 2002) of attaching mussels on the rocks has been used on both sites before the study by Mussel Rehabilitation Project. MRP staff has tried to rehabilitate both sites. The percentage cover was estimated, it was 5.65% in Lwandlana and 56.4% in Ocean after 6 months. This could not be verified in this study since all mussels were washed away on both sites in July soon after the removal of pipes. In this study the pipes were removed immediately after a month, in contrast in the Mussel Rehabilitation Project pipes were not removed immediately, they keep mussels under the pipes for longer time until more byssus threads are produced (MRP, personal communication).

The water movement was high and similar in Lwandlana, Ocean and Macosana (Table 5), while MRP staff considered Ocean and Macosana as good sites for rehabilitation success. Mthini West has similar water movement to Nqutheni ($p > 0.05$), while MRP staff considered Nqutheni as a good site for rehabilitation and Mthini North as a bad site. In the study it was possible to find good site with high water movement and good site with low water movement and *vice versa*.

Table 5. Sites arranged according to the degree of water movement from high to low water movement.

Wave action	Site	Rehabilitation Status
High water movement	Macosana	-Good
High water movement	Lwandlana	-Bad
High water movement	Ocean	-Good
Low water movement	Mthini West	-Bad
Low water movement	Nqutheni	-Good
Low water movement	Mthini East	-Bad

Nqutheni has the highest rehabilitation success among all the sites in Coffee Bay, and also the highest average wave force ($F = 75,895 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$). Other sites have lower wave force ranging between $17,306 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$ and $24,589 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$. Wave force was too high in Nqutheni due to 1 dynamometer which recorded much wave force. When this dynamometer was removed from the data, wave force remained high in Nqutheni ($28,250 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$). The good sites for rehabilitation had higher wave force than the bad sites for rehabilitation (Table 6).

Table 6. Sites arranged according to the degree of wave force from high to low wave force.

Wave action	Site	Rehabilitation Status
High wave force	Nqutheni	-Good
Low wave force	Macosana	-Good
Low wave force	Ocean	-Good
Low wave force	Lwandlana	-Bad
Low wave force	Mthini North	-Bad
Low wave force	Mthini South	-Bad

In this study the wave force was much higher than that reported in other studies (Palumbi 1984; Steffani & Branch (2003b). In Palumbi (1984) the maximum force recorded was $6,500 \text{ m}^{-2}$, in Steffani & Branch (2003b) the maximum force recorded was about $16,000 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$. In fact, the dynamometers in Palumbi (1984) were constructed using small cable ties (100mm). At the beginning of this study dynamometers were constructed using small cables ties (115mm). However those dynamometers could not be used in the second month and thereafter because wave force was able to push the head of the cable ties throughout the tab. New dynamometers were constructed using longer cable ties marked at 265mm. In September the wave force was so high that it was possible for the head of one of those dynamometers to travel a length of 247mm indicating a force of $647,629 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$.

The higher wave forces found along the coast of Coffee Bay could be due to the effect of Agulhas Current. The continental shelf is narrow along the Eastern Cape with a steep and narrow shelf slope. The Agulhas Current flows over the outer edge of the continental shore between Durban and Port Elizabeth and it flows close to the shore (Lubke & de Moor 1998). The current is usually strongest at the sea side of the shelf edge with an average rate of 3 knots and abnormal waves are possible. The continental shelf is narrowest along the Wild Coast, and very rough seas and waves are reported.

Wave action is known as one of the disturbances on the rocky shores. It has been reported to cause dislodgment of mussels from the rocky shores (Steffani & Branch 2003a) and more energy might be needed for maintenance. On the other hand larva settlement increases where there is high water flow (Borthagaray & Carranza 2007) and there are better feeding opportunities (Dahlhof & Menge 1996). Therefore, the problem depends on the degree of wave action, severe wave forces result in negative growth, while moderate wave action results in positive growth. Results from this study suggested that high wave forces are needed for successful mussel rehabilitation.

MRP staff as local harvesters were unable to rank all the sites because they were not familiar with all the sites. Local knowledge develops through observation and beliefs that do not originate from scientific expertise (Failing *et al.* 2007). Harvesters and MRP staff from the South of Coffee Bay do not use sites on the North of Coffee Bay and *vice versa*. Local people only harvest from the nearest site to their homes, therefore there is no direct link between local people and the distant sites. Local knowledge could not be helpful in ranking sites according to local perception of wave action in this study, because local knowledge emerges when people become familiar to the environment (Charnley *et al.* 2007). People can only rank sites that they were using, so they were unable to rank all the sites. It was important to include local knowledge in this study, local knowledge played a crucial role in management of rehabilitated sites in Coffee Bay. Its incorporation to this study would play an important role in the empowerment of the local people. Incorporation of local knowledge in biodiversity conservation has been widely recognised (Charnley *et al.* 2007) for conservation of natural resources.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Mthini East, Mthini West and Lwandlana are located in the north of Coffee Bay (figure 1), and are regarded as bad sites for rehabilitation by MRP staff, but there are some other sites between them which are considered as good for rehabilitation, similarly Ocean, Macosana and Nqutheni are located in the south and are regarded as good sites for rehabilitation, but there are other sites between them that are considered as bad, therefore geographical area has no effect on the rehabilitation success. If there were no good sites in the north and bad sites in the south I would suggest that north of Coffee Bay is not good for rehabilitation and I would look at the substrate type among other factors. The good sites in the north of Coffee Bay were not selected for the study because their accessibility is not easy.

Although it was possible to find good sites and bad sites with high water movement and *vice versa* there was a correlation between water movement and rehabilitation success. Wave force was higher in sites that were considered as good sites for rehabilitation, and there was a strong correlation between wave force and rehabilitation success. Therefore MRP should select sites with high wave action for rehabilitation of *P.perna* in Coffee Bay. The null hypothesis is rejected, wave action has an effect in mussel rehabilitation of mussels *P. perna* in Coffee Bay.

7. REFERENCES:

- ALFARO, A. C. 2006. Byssal attachment of juvenile mussels, *Perna canaliculus*, affected by water motion and air bubbles. *Aquaculture*. **255**: 357-361.
- AVERY, R. & ETTER, R. J. 2006. Microstructural differences in the reinforcement of a gastropod shell against predation. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*. **323**: 159–170.
- BAYNE, B. L. 1976. *Marine mussels: their ecology and physiology*. Cambridge University Press. London.
- BEADMAN, H. A., KAISER, M. J., GALANIDI, M., SHUCKSMITH, R & WILLOWS, R. I. 2004. Changes in species richness with stocking density of marine bivalves. *Journal of Applied Ecology*. **41**: 464-475.
- BORTHAGARAY, I. A. & CARRANZA, A. 2007. Mussels as ecosystem engineers: Their contribution to species richness in a rocky littoral community. *Acta Oecologica*. **31**: 243-250.
- CHARNLEY, S., FISCHER, A. P. & JONES, E. T. 2007. Integrating traditional and local ecological knowledge into forest biodiversity conservation in the Pacific Northwest. *Forest Ecology and Management*. **246**: 14-28.
- CHEUNG, S. G., LAM, S., GAO, Q. F., MAK, K. K. & SHIN, P. K. S. 2004. Induce anti-predator responses of the green mussel, *Perna viridis* (L.), on exposed to the predatory gastropod, *Thais clavigera* Kuster, and the swimming crab, *Thalamita danae* Stimpson. *Marine Biology*. **144**: 675-684.
- CINNER, J.E. & ASWANI, S. 2007. Integrating customary management into marine conservation. *Biological Conservation*. **140**: 201-216.
- DAHLHOFF, E. P. & MENGE, B. A. 1996. Influence of phytoplankton concentration and wave exposure on the ecophysiology of *Mytilus californianus*. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*. **144**: 97-107.
- DENNY, M. W. 1999. Are there mechanical limits to size in wave-swept organisms? *Journal of Experimental Biology*. **202**: 3463–3467.
- DOTY, M. S. 1971. Measurement of water movement in reference to algal growth. *Botanica Marina*. **14**: 32-35.
- DYE, H. A. & DYANTYI, N. 2002. Reseeding of Mussels on denuded rocky shores: Preliminary studies with the Brown Mussel, *Perna perna*. *South African Journal of*

Marine Science. **24**: 65-70.

- ELEVITCH, C. R. 2004. *The Overstory Book: Cultivating Connections with Tree*. Permanent Agriculture Resources. USA.
- ERLANDSSON, J., MCQUAID, C. D. & KOSTYLEV, V. E. 2005. Contrasting spatial heterogeneity of sessile organisms within mussel (*Perna perna* L.) beds in relation to topographic variability. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. **314**: 79-97.
- ETTER, R. J. 1989. Life history variation in the intertidal snail *Nucella lapillus* across a wave exposure gradient. *Ecology*. **70**: 1857–1876.
- FAILING, L. GREGORY, R. & HARSTONE, M. 2007. Integrating science and local knowledge in environmental risk management: A decision-focused approach. *Ecological Economics*. **64**: 47-60.
- HELSON, J. G., PLEDGER, S. & GARDNER, P. A. 2007. Does differential particulate food supply explain the presence of mussels in the Wellington Harbour (New Zealand) and their absence on neighboring Cook Strait shores? *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*. **72**: 223-234.
- HOCKEY, P. A. R. & BOSMAN, A. L. 1986. Man as an intertidal predator in Transkei: disturbance, community convergence and management of a natural food resource. *Oikos* **46**: 3-14.
- KEPE, T. & KOBOKANA, S. 2008. The challenges of poverty reduction and environmental conservation in South Africa's Extended Public Works Programme (EPWP). *Applied Geography*. **XXX**: 1–8.
- LASIAK, T. 1991a. Is there evidence of over-exploitation of mussel stocks on the Transkei coast? *South African Journal of Marine Science*. **10**: 299-302.
- LASIAK, T. 1991b. The Susceptibility and/ or resilience of rocky Littoral Molluscs to Stock depletion by the indigenous coastal people of Transkei, Southern Africa. *Biological Conservation*. **56**: 245-264.
- LASIAK, T. 1993. The shellfish-gathering practices of indigenous coastal people in Transkei: patterns, preferences and perceptions. *Southern African Journal of Ethnology*. **16** (4): 115-119.
- LUBKE, R. & de MOOR, I. 1998. *Field guide to the Eastern & Southern Cape Coasts*. University of Cape Town Press in association with the Grahamstown Branch of The Wildlife and environment Society of Southern Africa. South Africa.

- McKILLUP, S. 2005. *Statistic Explained An Introductory Guide for Life Scientists*. Cambridge University Press. United Kingdom.
- McQUAID, C. D. & LINDSAY, T. L. 2000. Effect of wave exposure on growth and mortality rates of the mussel *Perna perna*: bottom-up regulation of intertidal populations. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*. **206**: 147–154.
- PALUMBI, S. R. 1984. Measuring intertidal wave forces. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. **81**:171-179.
- PORRI, F., MCQUAID, C. D. & RADLOFF, S. 2006. Temporal scales of variation in settlement and recruitment of the mussel *Perna perna* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. **332**: 178-187.
- PROWSE, T. A. A. & A. J. PILE. 2005. Phenotypic homogeneity of two intertidal snails across a wave exposure gradient in South Australia. *Marine Biology Research*. **1**: 176-/185.
- REN, J. S. & ROSS, A. H. 2005. Environmental influence on mussel growth: A dynamic energy budget model and its application to the greenshell mussel *Perna canaliculus*. *Ecological Modelling*.**189**: 347-362.
- RIUS, M., KAEHLER, S. & McQUAID, C. D. 2006. The relationship between human exploitation pressure and condition of mussel populations along the coast of South Africa. *South African Journal of Science* **102**: 130-136.
- RIUS, M. & McQUAID, C. D. 2006. Wave action and competitive interaction between the invasive mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and the indigenous *Perna perna* in South Africa. *Marine Biology* **150**: 69-78.
- RUPPERT, E. E. & BARNES R.D. 1994. *Invertebrates Zoology*. Thomson Learning, United States of America.
- RUPPERT, E. E., FOX, R. S. & BARNES, R. D. 2004. *Invertebrates Zoology*. Thomson, United States of America.
- SHIN, P. K. S., LIU, C. C. & LIU, Z. X., CHEUNG, S. G. 2008. Marine mussels *Brachidontes variabilis* selected smaller places of refuge and enhanced byssus production upon exposure to conspecific and heterospecific cues. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. **361**: 16-20.

- SIEGFRIED, W. R., HOCKEY, P. A. R. & CROWE, A. A. 1985. Exploitation and Conservation of Brown Mussel stocks by Coastal People of Transkei. *Environmental Conservation* 12(4): 302-307.
- SOKAL, R. R. & ROHLF, F. J. 1995. *Biometry*. W. H. Freeman and Company. USA.
- STEFFANI, C. N. & BRANCH, M. G. 2003a. Spatial comparisons of populations of an indigenous limpet *Scutellastra argenvillei* and alien mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* along a gradient of wave energy. *African Journal of Marine Science* **25**: 195-212.
- STEFFANI, C. N. & BRANCH, G. M. 2003b. Growth rate, condition, and shell shape of *Mytilus galloprovincialis*: responses to wave exposure. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* **246**: 197-209.
- STEFFANI, C. N. & BRANCH, M. G. 2003c. Temporal changes in an interaction between an indigenous limpet *Scutellastra argenvillei* and an alien mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*: effects of wave exposure. *African Journal of Marine Science* **25**: 213-229.
- TRUSSELL, G. D. & R. J. ETTER. 2001. Integrating genetic and environmental forces that shape the evolution of geographic variation in a marine snail. *Genetica*. **112**: 321-337.